

1 ***In silico* study to highlight modeling issues in bioscience**

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12 **Abstract**

13 Mathematical models are crucial in biology to understand biological mechanisms,
14 perform estimations and as decision-making tools for policy makers. Models face
15 numerous issues, and this study addresses three of them : data transformation (Issue
16 1), loss of power in variable effects identification (Issue 2) and omission of a factor
17 structuring the data consequences (Issue 3). Using models of enteric methane (CH₄)
18 emissions of ruminants, these issues were illustrated by simulating three scenarios.
19 Their impacts on regression coefficient (RC) estimation and on prediction accuracy
20 were investigated. Scenarios were simulated based on a reference model, using dry
21 matter intake (DMI), ether extract and fiber contents, and organic matter digestibility to
22 predict CH₄ emissions. Issue 1 highlighted that log-transformation may allow validating
23 the assumption of residuals homogeneity and improve prediction confidence.
24 Moreover, the interpretation of log-transformed RC was relevant in the study context.
25 Issue 2 revealed that RC were impacted differently according to the data variability
26 scenario. DMI showed high consistency, while other variables were less reliable about
27 RC estimations. Small datasets often failed to detect their effects, except for DMI. Issue
28 3 demonstrated that ignoring a factor affecting data, such as a mutation, led to biased
29 RC and predictions, even if this factor is greatly unbalanced. To conclude, this work
30 highlights three warnings: 1) the negative effect on statistical assumptions and
31 prediction confidence of not transforming data when required, 2) to carefully interpret
32 biological effects via RC as they can be highly impacted by data variability and do not
33 rely only on significance as a criterion for variable selection and 3) the strong bias on
34 RC and predictions caused by few atypical observations in data.

35 **Keywords:** Monte-Carlo simulations, Variability analysis, Data transformation, Power
36 analysis, Missing data

37 **1. Introduction**

38 Biological processes are composed of several interacting biological components. The
39 abundance and diversity of these components and their interactions led to highly
40 complex systems (Karplus, 1983; Motta and Pappalardo, 2012; Torres and Santos,
41 2015). Understanding biological systems implies *in vivo* and field experiments to
42 generate data. Mathematical modeling constitutes a widely used tool for analyzing
43 such data and managing their complexity, since models are a simplified representation
44 of the system under study. They proved powerful tools to better understand, quantify
45 and make decisions (Bedau, 1999; Haefner, 2005; Nitecki and Hoffman, 1987).

46 Numerous models are used in many scientific fields and several studies highlighted
47 the positive relation between the maturity of a scientific field and the common use of
48 mathematical models (Gunawardena, 2012; Medio, 2009; Weidlich, 2003). For
49 instance, in medical research, numerous models are developed in cancer research
50 (Vieira et al., 2023). Moreover, in chemistry the dynamics of the enzyme-catalyzed
51 subsequent reactions were represented in the Michaelis–Menten model (Michaelis and
52 Menten, 1913). Finally, in metabolic engineering, mathematical models are used to
53 inform scientists about the optimal conditions to cultivate cells or bacteria in order to
54 produce a chemical component of interest (Wendisch et al., 2006). Several
55 mathematical frameworks are available for modeling a biological system and the
56 statistical method used in practice is related to the nature of the system under study
57 (dynamic or static, for instance).

58 In the context of Climate Change, ruminant livestock systems play an important role
59 by emitting CH₄ through rumen fermentation. This complex biological mechanism
60 corresponds to the degradation of feed intake by the animal, thanks to a complex
61 microbial ecosystem in the rumen (Beauchemin et al., 2020; Morgavi et al., 2010).
62 These emissions represent 14.5% of total greenhouse gases from anthropic activities
63 (Gerber, 2013). Therefore, mitigation strategies must be developed to reduce
64 environmental burden of ruminants.

65 In this context, mathematical models are used to estimate this amount of CH₄, assess
66 mitigation strategies' efficiency and better understand rumen fermentation (Appuhamy
67 et al., 2016; Ellis et al., 2007; IPCC, 2019; Kebreab et al., 2008). Independent variables
68 used in these models can be related to animal characteristics, diet composition and
69 animal production. Availability of these data is very fluctuating from a variable to
70 another because their measurements are costly, time consuming and sometimes
71 their accuracy is low (Della Rosa et al., 2021; Hammond et al., 2016). Therefore,
72 datasets used to develop models are heterogeneous in terms of number of data
73 considered and range of variation explored. This makes difficult the comparison of
74 models developed with different datasets and interpretation of regression coefficients
75 (order of magnitude and sign).

76 Furthermore, the application of parametric statistical methods requires that data meet
77 several assumptions. For instance, a linear relationship between the dependent and
78 independent variables, the normality and homoscedasticity (i.e. homogeneity of
79 variance) of model's residuals are required to apply linear regression. In theory, all
80 these conditions must be met, but in practice, this is not always the case. Non respect
81 of these assumptions and poor data quality (noise, non representativeness, presence
82 of atypical points/outliers...) can lead to several issues, impacting model predictions
83 and conducting to misleading interpretations. Moreover, two sources of variation may
84 affect model predictions: (i) the variability of coefficient estimates according to the
85 dataset used for fitting the model and (ii) the variability of data itself, where each
86 independent variable may impact more or less severely the predictions, corresponding
87 to the study of independent variable sensitivity (Faivre et al., 2013).

88 Modeling issues are numerous (Hastie et al., 2009) and the objective of our study was
89 to address some of them. We selected those related to three main sources: 1) data
90 transformation, 2) lack of power to study the influence of independent variables and 3)
91 omission of a factor structuring the data such as a mutation affecting a part of the data.
92 Having a good knowledge of these potential issues and of their consequences is crucial
93 for modelers. Many courses describing modeling issues and proposing solutions to
94 consider and avoid them are available in the literature (James et al., 2021), however,
95 to our knowledge, no work using simulation tools to illustrate these issues was

96 proposed to the community. This study aims to illustrate these three modeling issues
97 commonly met in biology and what are their implications, using Monte-Carlo
98 simulations. Based on case study analysis of three different scenarios, their impacts
99 on model predictions will also be studied using simulations generated by mathematical
100 models computing methane (CH₄) emissions produced by ruminants.

101 **2. Material and methods**

102 The general approach conducted in our work is described in Fig. 1. We investigated
103 three modeling issues by developing three simulation scenarios. The three issues
104 studied were: 1) the data transformation (Issue 1), 2) the loss of power of
105 independent variables (Issue 2) and 3) the omission of a mutation in the data (Issue
106 3). In addition, the three simulation scenarios conducted were: 1) the data variability
107 scenarios (Simulation scenario 1) by simulating 1000 datasets of 500 observations
108 each associated with a different variability, 2) the mutation scenarios (Simulation
109 scenario 2) by simulating 1000 datasets of 500 observations each with the presence
110 of a mutation affecting the small ruminants and 3) the missing data scenarios
111 (Simulation scenario 3) by randomly subsampling the datasets simulated with
112 Simulation scenario 1 and 2. Issue 1 was investigated before the development of
113 simulation scenarios. Whereas, Issue 2 was investigated using Simulation scenario 1
114 and 3. Finally, Issue 3 was investigated using Simulation scenario 2 and 3.
115

Fig. 1. Summary of the approach developed in our study

116

117 2.1. The case study

118 Models of enteric CH₄ emissions developed in ERA-NETGas Project “CEDERS”
 119 provided in the open access database were used for conducting the simulations
 120 (Benaouda et al., 2019a). The database is composed of several selected studies
 121 reporting dietary treatment features means associated with contrasted diets, which
 122 aimed to mitigate enteric CH₄ emissions, and quantified excretions from ruminants (de
 123 Ondarza et al., 2023). Therefore, each observation corresponds to recorded means

124 associated with a dietary treatment within a study. Several ruminant categories were
125 considered: small and large ruminants. Models developed with these data in the study
126 of Benaouda et al. (2019a) were linear mixed-effect models with a random effect
127 related to the study.

128 **2.2. Issue 1: Data transformation**

129 *2.2.1. Objectives of data transformation*

130 Statistical parametric methods require that data meet several assumptions. Data
131 transformation is commonly used to help data reach these assumptions (Bartlett, 1947;
132 Berry, 1987; Manly, 1976; Ribeiro-Oliveira et al., 2018). However, from a practical point
133 of view, the biological interpretation of regression coefficients associated with the
134 independent variables and then predictions is sometimes difficult, once data are
135 transformed (Ribeiro-Oliveira et al., 2018). Therefore, it is essential to ensure the
136 interpretability of the new regression coefficients and to back transform predictions
137 (Lee, 2020).

138 A common transformation used for skewed data is the logarithmic transformation
139 (Bartlett, 1947; Berry, 1987; Ford, 2018). This transformation allows to spread out
140 grouped data and bring together spread-out data. CEDERS data revealed a linear
141 relationship between CH₄ production (g/day) and dry matter intake per day (DMI,
142 kg/day), but also an heterogeneity of variance (heteroscedasticity) associated with
143 small and large ruminant populations (Fig. 6). A logarithmic transformation of these
144 two variables was therefore conducted. To investigate the impact of logarithmic
145 transformation when developing a model, linear regressions between CH₄ and DMI
146 were fitted with original and log-transformed data for comparing coefficients of
147 determination (R²) and residual plots. Confidence intervals (CI) were also compared
148 for assessing uncertainty around the estimates of both regression coefficients.

149 The logarithmic transformation of CH₄ and DMI led to a new interpretation of the
150 regression coefficients (Ford, 2018). Usually, a regression coefficient β_i associated
151 with an independent variable x_i indicates increase/decrease of the dependent variable
152 y for one-unit increase of x_i . Considering the logarithmic transformation, if only y is
153 log-transformed, then $(e^{\beta_i} - 1) \times 100$ gives the percentage of increase/decrease of y
154 for every one-unit increase of x_i . Whereas, if both x_i and y are log-transformed then β_i
155 can directly be interpreted as the percentage of increase/decrease of y for every 1%
156 increase of x_i value. In our case study, this interpretation seemed more appropriate
157 than the usual interpretation of regression coefficients.

158 *2.2.2. Impact of data transformation on model predictions*

159 The impact of the logarithmic transformation of CH₄ and DMI on model predictions was
160 also investigated. Therefore, the comparison of predictions between linear regressions
161 fitted with original and log-transformed data were conducted. A Leave-One Out (LOO)
162 cross validation approach (James et al., 2014) was used for assessing the predictive
163 performances of both regressions. Folds selected were individual studies composing
164 the CEDERS data (n = 145 studies). Root mean square prediction error (RMSPE;
165 Bibby and Toutenburg (1977)) to standard deviation ratio (RSR) and concordance
166 correlation coefficients (CCC; Lin (1989)) were computed to compare the predictive
167 performances. A model with good predictive performances is associated with a low
168 RSR and a high CCC. Moriasi et al. (2007) qualified an RSR < 0.5 as “very good” and
169 close to 1.0 as “unsatisfactory”. The CCC indicates the concordance between
170 observed and predicted values, a value close to 1 is associated with better model

171 performance. In addition, prediction uncertainty of both regressions was investigated
 172 by comparing CIs of predictions.

173 The predictions computed using the regression fitted with log-transformed data were
 174 log-scaled. Therefore, these predictions were back transformed in g/day. We might
 175 think that simply exponentiating the log-scaled predictions is sufficient to perform the
 176 back transformation. However, this technique provides biased predictions at the initial
 177 scale (Wheeler, 2020). This issue is called the retransformation problem. Therefore,
 178 we back transformed the predictions by using the Duan's Smearing Estimator (= $\exp(\widehat{\log(y)}) \cdot \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \exp(\epsilon_i)$, with ϵ_i the residuals), which is a non-biased estimator
 179 (Duan, 1983).
 180

181 **2.3. Definition of simulation scenarios** Selection of a reference model describing
 182 the "true" relationship between CH₄ production (g/d) and biological variables

183 Among the different models developed in the case study (Benaouda et al., 2019a), one
 184 model was selected based on its low prediction error (RSR = 0.30) and its selected
 185 independent variables. It described the assumed "true" biological relationships
 186 between CH₄ emissions and biological variables, describing feed intake and diet
 187 composition fed to animals. We may call it the true model generating data. The
 188 reference model selected used DMI (kg/d), dietary ether extract content (EE, %DM),
 189 dietary fiber content (NDF, %DM) and organic matter digestibility (OMD, %) to predict
 190 CH₄ production of ruminants (Table 1, model [1]). As there is no structuration by "study"
 191 anymore, no random effect related to the study of the original model were considered
 192 in this case, and the model was fitted again with both CH₄ emissions and DMI log-
 193 transformed (Table 1, model [2]), based on the recommendations highlighted in Issue
 194 1 (cf. section 2.2).
 195

195 **Table 1**

196 Reference model of enteric methane (CH₄) production (g/day) and performance
 197 assessment from A) the database (original data) and B) the log-transformation of CH₄
 198 and dry matter intake per day (DMI, kg/day).

Reference model	n	RSR
A) Original data $CH_4 = -108 (-202, -14.4) + 19.7 (18.5, 20.8) \times DMI - 0.62 (-0.86, -0.38) \times EE + 0.12 (0.05, 0.19) \times NDF + 139 (40.8, 237) \times OMD$ [1]	245	0.30
B) Log-transformation of CH ₄ and DMI $\text{Log } CH_4 = 2.21 (1.73, 2.68) + 0.98 (0.94, 1.02) \times \text{Log } DMI - 0.03 (-0.04, -0.02) \times EE + 0.008 (0.004, 0.01) \times NDF + 0.009 (0.004, 0.01) \times OMD$ [2]	245	0.22

199 CH₄ = methane production (g/day); DMI = dry matter intake (kg/day); EE = dietary ether extract content
 200 (%DM); NDF = dietary neutral detergent fiber content (%DM); OMD = organic matter digestibility (%);
 201 Log CH₄ = logarithm of the methane production; Log DMI = logarithm of the dry matter intake; n =
 202 number of observations; RSR = root mean square prediction error (RMSPE) to standard deviation ratio

203 **2.3.2. Simulation scenario 1 : Data variability scenarios**

204 To simulate realistic datasets, the Probability Density Functions (PDF) of variables
 205 DMI, EE, NDF and OMD were fitted from CEDERS data using the fitdistrplus R
 206 package (Delignette-Muller, 2014, R Core Team versions 4.1.2). Several distributions
 207 were tested for each variable and were selected if they had the highest goodness of fit
 208 and lowest Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC). PDF fitted to DMI, EE, NDF and OMD
 209 were displayed in Table 2.

210 **Table 2**

211 Probability Distribution Function of dry matter intake (DMI; kg/day), dietary ether
 212 extract content (EE; %DM), dietary fiber content (NDF; %DM) and organic matter
 213 digestibility (OMD; %) fitted on the overall population, and small and large ruminants
 214 subpopulations of the database.

Variables	Probability Distribution Function
Overall population	
DMI (kg/d)	$0.33 \times \text{LogN}(-0.04, 0.42) + 0.29 \times \text{Weibull}(3.72, 8.37) + 0.38 \times \text{N}(2.92, 0.17)$
EE (%DM)	$\text{LogN}(1.33, 0.48)$
NDF (%DM)	$\text{N}(39.6, 12.0)$
OMD (%)	$\text{Weibull}(10.6, 73.5)$
Small ruminants subpopulation	
DMI (kg/d)	$\text{LogN}(-0.07, 0.38)$
EE (%DM)	$\text{LogN}(1.27, 0.46)$
NDF (%DM)	$\text{Weibull}(3.31, 44.9)$
OMD (%)	$\text{Gamma}(63.4, 0.90)$
Large ruminants subpopulation	
DMI (kg/d)	$0.43 \times \text{Weibull}(3.47, 7.92) + 0.57 \times \text{Gamma}(31.7, 1.69)$
EE (%DM)	$\text{LogN}(1.35, 0.48)$
NDF (%DM)	$\text{N}(39.4, 11.6)$
OMD (%)	$\text{Weibull}(12.0, 73.2)$

215 DMI = dry matter intake (kg/day); EE = dietary ether extract content (%DM); NDF = dietary neutral
 216 detergent fiber content (%DM); OMD = organic matter digestibility (%).
 217 Five hundred values were randomly drawn from fitted distributions for each
 218 independent variables (DMI, EE, NDF and OMD) to build each simulated dataset.
 219 Then, CH₄ production was computed using the reference model formula (Table 1,
 220 model [2]) for the 500 simulated sets of predictors values. A noise (disturbance error)
 221 was added when computing CH₄ values, by randomly drawing 500 values from a
 222 normal distribution centered on 0, with a standard deviation equal to the reference
 223 model residuals' one (ϵ_{Ref}) ($\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\epsilon_{\text{Ref}}})$). Objective of the added random noise was to
 224 reproduce perturbations/residuals observed in real data. In reality, these
 225 perturbations may be caused by several factors, such as measurement methods,
 226 experimental design or individual variability of animals used in *in vivo* experiment
 227 (Hammond et al., 2016). The result was a dataset of 500 observations constituting
 228 one scenario of data variability (e.g. log(CH₄) vs. log(DMI) in Fig. 2). This process
 229 was repeated 1000 times, generating 1000 scenarios or plausible sampled datasets
 230 of data variability (Simulation scenario 1).
 231

Fig. 2. Log-transformed methane production (Log CH₄; no unit) vs. log-transformed dry matter intake (Log DMI; no unit) plot of one scenario of data variability (Simulation scenario 1).

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233 *2.3.3. Simulation scenario 2: Presence of a « mutation » affecting small*
 234 *ruminants*

235 The second simulation scenario developed was what we called a “mutation” affecting
 236 small ruminants. In reality, an example of this so called “mutation” can be related to
 237 several factors and seen as a genetic modification, a disease or different management
 238 practices for small ruminants. To consider this mutation, the reference model
 239 computing CH₄ production (Table 1, model [2]) was slightly modified. When predicting
 240 large ruminant data, the reference model (Table 1, model [2]) was used without any
 241 changes. Whereas, when predicting small ruminant data, a different intercept arbitrary
 242 chosen (1 instead of 2.21) was considered in the reference model, regression
 243 coefficients of DMI, EE, NDF and OMD remaining unchanged. The aim was to see how
 244 one single modification in the model (intercept in that case) can impact the analyses.
 245 The PDFs of DMI, EE, NDF and OMD associated with small and large ruminants (two
 246 different populations) were fitted using the same approach as Simulation scenario 1
 247 and were displayed in Table 2. Hence, 1000 datasets of 500 observations each with a
 248 50%/50% distribution between small (mutated individuals) and large (non-mutated
 249 individuals) ruminants were simulated, by randomly drawing 500 values in the
 250 respective distributions of DMI, EE, NDF and OMD, and by computing CH₄ production
 251 with the appropriate equation and a gaussian noise $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{\epsilon_{\text{Ref}}})$ (Simulation scenario
 252 2), similarly to Simulation scenario 1. The result was a dataset of 500 observations
 253 composed of 250 small and large ruminants, constituting one scenario of data affected
 254 by a mutation (e.g. log(CH₄) vs. log(DMI) in Fig. 3).

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Fig. 3. Log-transformed methane production (Log CH₄; no unit) vs. log-transformed dry matter intake (Log DMI; no unit) plot of one scenario simulating the presence of a mutation affecting small ruminants (Simulation scenario 2).

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In addition, other datasets were simulated by changing the distribution between small and large ruminants. Percentage of small ruminants in the population was gradually increased from 10 to 90% with a step of 10%, and 1000 datasets of 500 observations each were simulated for each level of increase (e.g. log(CH₄) vs. log(DMI) in Fig. 4).

Ruminants type · Large ruminants · Small ruminants (Mutated population)

Fig. 4. Log-transformed methane production (Log CH₄; no unit) vs. log-transformed dry matter intake (Log DMI; no unit) plot of two scenarios simulating the presence of a mutation affecting small ruminants with A) 10% of small ruminants in the population and B) 90% of small ruminants in the population (Simulation scenario 2)

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2.3.4. Simulation scenario 3 : Missing data scenarios

264 Missing data scenarios were developed by randomly sub-sampling each dataset
265 simulated in Simulation scenario 1 and 2 (Simulation scenario 3). Observations
266 removed were randomly drawn considering the 500 observations in Simulation
267 scenario 1, and only the small ruminants (250 observations) in Simulation scenario 2.
268 Several thresholds of missing data, ranging from 10 to 90% and 10 to 100% were
269 considered in Simulation scenario 1 and 2, respectively. Therefore, for Simulation
270 scenario 1 and 2, each threshold was associated with 1000 missing data scenarios,
271 with missing observations ranging from 50 to 450 and 25 to 250 in Simulation scenario
272 1 and 2, respectively.

273 **2.4. Issue 2: Loss of power of independent variables** In statistics, the term loss
274 of power can be used in different situations. In this work, the loss of power
275 refers to the risk of a decrease in the probability of detecting the effect of a
276 variable.

277 *2.4.1. Variability of regression coefficients and significance of variables*

278 Multiple linear regressions using independent variables DMI, EE, NDF and OMD were
279 developed on each dataset from Simulation scenario 1 and 3 (cf. 2.3.2 and 2.3.4).
280 Estimated regression coefficients, and corresponding CIs and p-values, associated
281 with each independent variable were recovered. The variability of estimated regression
282 coefficients was analyzed by computing summary statistics and the coefficient of
283 variation (CV%), and by plotting boxplots of estimates distributions. This variability
284 analysis refers to the study of variable consistency. This term will be used throughout
285 the manuscript.

286 Moreover, the impact of each independent variable on the CH₄ emission response
287 variable was also analyzed through the percentage of models considering this variable
288 as statistically non-significant at 5% level (i.e. p-value > 0.05) over the pool of available
289 datasets in Simulation scenario 1. Finally, evolution of this percentage according to the
290 respective threshold of missing data considered in the datasets of Simulation scenario
291 3 was studied.

292 *2.4.2. Sampling and model prediction variability*

293 We conducted two analyses to assess the impact of variability, (i) from the regression
294 coefficient estimates with respects to sampling fluctuation of Simulation scenario 1
295 datasets (analysis 1) and (ii) from the sampling fluctuation of independent variables
296 itself (analysis 2), on model predictions. For both analyses, two cases were
297 considered: (i) the “all at once” case where the element studied (regression coefficients
298 (analysis 1) or independent variables (analysis 2)) varied all together for Log DMI, EE,
299 NDF and OMD (case 1), and (ii) the “one at a time” case where the element studied
300 varied one after another for Log DMI, EE, NDF and OMD (case 2). The approach
301 conducted is summarized in Fig. 5.

302

Fig. 5. Summary of the approach developed to investigate the impact of the loss of power of independent variables (Issue 2) on model predictions.

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In analysis 1, we predicted CH₄ production using the collection of model coefficients fitted over the pool of datasets from Simulation scenario 1. Variables Log DMI, EE, NDF and OMD were set to their mean values from the CEDERS database, and we used regression coefficients estimated from each model developed with datasets from Simulation scenario 1. We used each model set of coefficients for case 1, and by setting three of them to reference model values (Table 1, model [2]), we used only the coefficient estimates of one independent variable for case 2. In analysis 2, we did the opposite. We always used the “true” regression coefficient values of the reference model (Table 1, model [2]) and let only independent variable

313 values vary across Simulation scenario 1 datasets. All predictor values from each
314 dataset were considered for case 1, but we set three independent variables to their
315 mean values from CEDERS database and let only the fourth variable values vary
316 across Simulation scenario 1 datasets for case 2. We repeated the case 2 approach
317 for each predictor, one after the other. Variability of CH₄ predictions was studied by
318 computing CV% values from both analyses.

319 **2.5. Issue 3: Omission of a mutation in the data**

320 *2.5.1. Impact on regression coefficient estimations*

321 Three new models were developed with datasets from Simulation scenario 2 and 3 (cf.
322 2.3.3 and 2.3.4), using the same formula than the reference's one as a basis (Table 1,
323 model [2]). The first model considered the mutation as an additional fifth predictor
324 (model 1). The second one didn't account for the mutation (model 2), and the third was
325 fitted only with the small ruminant (mutated) part of datasets (model 3).

326 Again, estimated regression coefficients, and corresponding CIs and p-values, were
327 recovered for models 1, 2 and 3. Summary statistics and CV% values assessed the
328 variability of estimated regression coefficients. We also assessed the variability of
329 estimated regression coefficients according to the threshold of missing data to study
330 the impact of mutant proportion in the dataset.

331 Finally, the mutant CH₄ emission predictive accuracy of the three models was
332 compared through their RSR on a test dataset only composed of small ruminants, i.e.
333 mutant individuals.

334 *2.5.2. Impact on models' predictive performance*

335 We also ran analysis 1 (case 1 and 2) from point 2.4.2 to assess model prediction
336 variability and accuracy using model 1 and model 2 over Simulation scenario 2
337 datasets.

338 **3. Results**

339 **3.1. Issue 1: Data transformation**

340 *3.1.1. Interest of data transformation and application to CEDERS data*

341 Fig. 6 illustrated how logarithmic transformation of data scattered low values from small
342 ruminants and grouped dispersed values from large ruminants, allowing the
343 heteroscedastic dispersion to become an homoscedastic one along a linear
344 relationship.

345

Fig. 6. Methane production (CH_4 ; g/day) vs. dry matter intake per day (DMI; kg/day) plot from A) original data of the database and B) log-transformed data (Log CH_4 and Log DMI; no unit).

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347 Linear regressions fitted between CH_4 and DMI on original and log-transformed data
 348 (models not shown) indicated a slightly better goodness of fit for the model developed
 349 with transformed data with an increase of R^2 from 0.91 to 0.95. Moreover, regarding
 350 the CIs of coefficient estimates, regression fitted with log-transformed data was
 351 associated with much less uncertainty for the intercept estimate. Moreover, for DMI
 352 coefficient, the regression fitted with log-transformed data was associated with less
 353 uncertainty around the estimate, although CV% were almost similar between both
 354 regressions (1.77% vs 2.46%, respectively).

355 Residual plots associated with both regressions (Fig. 7) confirmed the need to log-
 356 transform the data in order to meet the assumptions underlying linear regression
 357 models. However, transformation changed the biological meaning of model
 358 coefficients.

359

Fig. 7. Residuals plot of linear regressions between methane production (CH₄; g/day) and dry matter intake per day (DMI; kg/day) fitted on A) original data of the database and B) log-transformed data (Log CH₄ and Log DMI; no unit).

360
 361 In the reference model considered to run the simulation scenarios (Table 1, model
 362 [2]), CH₄ and DMI were log-transformed, leading to a new interpretation of the
 363 regression coefficients. Therefore, for the model fitted on original data, an increase of
 364 1 kg/day of DMI and of 1% of NDF and OMD led to an increase of 19.7, 0.12 and 139
 365 g/day of CH₄, respectively. Moreover, an increase of 1% of EE in the diet led to a
 366 decrease of 0.62 g/day of CH₄. Whereas, after a log-transformation of CH₄ and DMI,
 367 an increase of 1% of DMI, NDF and OMD led to an increase of 0.98%, 0.80% (= 100
 368 x (e^{0.008} - 1)) and 0.90% (= 100 x (e^{0.009} - 1)) of Log CH₄, respectively. Moreover, an
 369 increase of 1% of EE led to a decrease of 3% (= 100 x (e^{0.03} - 1)) of Log CH₄.

3.1.2. Impact of data transformation on model predictive performance

370
 371 Table 3 displays LOO cross-validation method evaluation criteria assessing the
 372 predictive performance of linear regressions between CH₄ and DMI from original or
 373 log-transformed CEDERS data. It exhibits model performances for three datasets that
 374 gather all data or separate small and large ruminant samples.

Table 3

375
 376 Predictive performances of linear regressions between enteric methane (CH₄)
 377 production (g/day) and dry matter intake per day (DMI, kg/day) assessed by a leave-
 378 one out cross validation developed with A) original data from the database and B) log-
 379 transformation of CH₄ and DMI.

Linear regressions between CH ₄ and DMI development	n	RSR	CCC
All the data			
A) Original data [1]	629	0.30	0.95
B) Log-transformed data [2]	629	0.31	0.95
Small ruminant population			
A) Original data [3]	201	0.89	0.67
B) Log-transformed data [4]	201	0.80	0.71
Large ruminant population			
A) Original data [5]	428	0.44	0.89
B) Log-transformed data [6]	428	0.45	0.90

380 CH₄ = methane production (g/day); DMI = dry matter intake (kg/day); n = number of observations; RSR
381 = root mean square prediction error (RMSPE) to standard deviation ratio; CCC = Lin's concordance
382 correlation coefficient

383 RSR and CCC indicated a similar ability to predict all the data and large ruminant
384 samples for both regressions. However, we need to remember that the former didn't
385 meet homoscedasticity assumption underlying linear regression model. When all the
386 data were considered (Table 3, [1] and [2]), the prediction error was low (RSR = 0.30
387 and 0.31, respectively) and concordance between observed and predicted values was
388 high (CCC = 0.95 for both regressions). Whereas, when only large ruminant samples
389 were considered (Table 3, [5] and [6]), RSR increased (= 0.44 and 0.45, respectively)
390 and CCC decreased (= 0.89 and 0.90, respectively), even if performances were still
391 very satisfactory.

392 Evaluation over small ruminant samples (Table 3, [3] and [4]) highlighted a difference
393 in performance between both regressions, with a lower RSR (0.78 vs 0.89) and a
394 higher CCC (0.71 vs 0.67) for the one fitted with log-transformed data, indicating a
395 better predictive ability for this model. However, the RSR close to 1 highlighted an
396 unsatisfactory ability of both regressions to predict small ruminant sample data.
397 Reasons behind these observations are described in the following sections of the
398 article.

399 Regarding the confidence of both regressions in their predictions, Fig. 8 indicated that
400 the band of upper and lower bounds of CIs around the prediction was much more
401 narrower for the regression developed with log-transformed data compared to the one
402 developed with original data for the small ruminant individuals. This highlighted that
403 the confidency level of the regression developed with the original data was very poor,
404 while it was very high for the regression developed with log-transformed data, when
405 predicting this subpopulation. In addition, this band was similar between both
406 regressions for the large ruminant individuals. However, the regression developed with
407 the original data showed a narrower band for the very high values of CH₄ and DMI,
408 highlighting a higher confidency for the very high CH₄ producer animals. These results
409 were consistent with those obtained with Table 3.

Fig. 8. Methane production (CH_4 ; g/day) vs. dry matter intake per day (DMI; kg/day) plot from observed data for A) the small ruminants of the database and B) the large ruminants of the database (grey points). Predictions and associated confidence intervals of linear regressions between enteric methane (CH_4) production (g/day) and dry matter intake per day (DMI, kg/day) developed with original data (black lines) from the database and log-transformation of CH_4 and DMI (red lines) were displayed.

410

411 **3.2. Issue 2: Loss of power of independent variables**

412 3.2.1. Variability of regression coefficients and significance of variables

413 This section addresses the differences departures of regression coefficient estimates
 414 from their real values according to the dataset used to compute them. Actually, the
 415 sampling process led to a slightly different estimated value of a given coefficient for
 416 each dataset from Simulation scenario 1. The reference model gave us the “real” value
 417 of coefficients.

418 Fig. 9 reports coefficient estimates divided by the respective reference “real value” for
 419 each independent variable across all Simulation scenario 1 datasets. Moreover, the
 420 minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation and CV% from estimations of each
 421 regression coefficient are presented in Table 4.

422

Fig. 9. Estimated regression coefficients divided by the respective regression coefficient from the reference model (i.e. the “true” values) for the following predictors: log-transformed dry matter intake per day (Log DMI, no unit), dietary ether extract content (EE, %), dietary neutral detergent fiber content (NDF, %) and organic matter digestibility (OMD, %). Linear regression models were fitted using datasets from Simulation scenario 1. The red dotted line at 1 represents the case when estimate = “true” coefficient.

423

424

Table 4

425 Summary statistics of estimated regression coefficients of models developed with
 426 datasets from Simulation scenario 1.

Variable	Min	Mean	SD	Max	CV%
Log DMI	0.95	0.98	0.01	1.01	0.86
EE	-0.06	-0.03	0.005	-0.01	17.5
NDF	0.005	0.008	0.0009	0.01	11.7
OMD	0.004	0.009	0.001	0.01	16.0

427 Log DMI = logarithm of dry matter intake; EE = dietary ether extract content (%); NDF = dietary neutral
 428 detergent fiber content (%); OMD = organic matter digestibility (%); Min = minimum; SD = standard
 429 deviation; Max = maximum; CV% = coefficient of variation = $\left(\frac{SD}{Mean}\right) \times 100$

430 The CV%-values indicated that Log DMI were largely associated with the lowest
 431 variability around the “true” value (CV% = 0.86%), highlighting a strong consistency of
 432 this variable. Whereas, EE, NDF and OMD showed a much higher sensitivity to the
 433 noise simulated in Simulation scenario 1 with CV% of 17.5%, 11.7% and 16.0%,
 434 respectively.

435 As expected, introduction of missing data (Simulation scenario 3) in datasets from
 436 Simulation scenario 1 increased the variability of estimated regression coefficients
 437 around the “true” value for the 4 variables considered (Fig. 10).

438

Fig. 10. Boxplots of estimated regression coefficients associated with predictors: log-transformed dry matter intake per day (Log DMI, no unit), dietary ether extract content (EE, %), dietary neutral detergent fiber content (NDF, %) and organic matter digestibility (OMD, %). Linear regression models were fitted using datasets from Simulation scenario 3 and missing data thresholds 10%, 50% and 90% respectively. The red dotted line represents regression coefficients from the reference model (i.e. the “true” value).

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However, the same proportions of missing data did not impact similarly the rate of statistical significance at the 95% level of confidence according to the independent variable considered (Fig. 11).

Fig. 11. Percentage (%) of non-significant regression coefficients for predictors: log-transformed dry matter intake per day (Log DMI, no unit), dietary ether extract content (EE, %), dietary neutral detergent fiber content (NDF, %) and organic matter digestibility (OMD, %) according to the percentage (%) of missing data. The used datasets are from Simulation scenario 3.

444 Hence, Log DMI was always associated with a significant coefficient, even when only
 445 50 observations were available (90% of missing data in the datasets from Simulation
 446 scenario 1) for the models' fitting, confirming its consistency. Whereas, the percentage
 447 of models associated with a statistically non-significant coefficient increased for other
 448 variables, for thresholds of missing data above 40%. Over 50% of the models showed
 449 non-significant regression coefficients for EE and OMD when developed with only 50
 450 observations. The impact of missing data on statistical significance for NDF was less
 451 important than for EE and OMD, with only 27% of non-significant coefficients for the
 452 models developed with 50 observations.
 453

454 3.2.2. Impact of Simulation scenario 1 on model prediction variability

455 In analysis 1, different coefficient estimates led to different predicted values for CH₄
 456 emissions. Fig. 12 reveals distribution of these predictions according to the coefficient
 457 estimate distributions, using sets of estimated coefficients for all the independent
 458 variables (case 1; A) or of only one independent variable where coefficients for other
 459 variables remained to the reference model's values (case 2; B).
 460

Fig. 12. Boxplots of CH₄ (g/d) predicted with models developed with datasets from Simulation scenario 1 (analysis 1). Independent variables are set to their mean value from the CEDERS project database. In case 1 (A), each model gives one prediction, using its own set of estimated coefficients (estimated coefficients vary all together). In case 2 (B), estimated coefficients vary one after the other. Coefficients from the reference model are used to do the prediction, except for the regression coefficient of log-transformed dry matter intake per day (Log DMI, no unit), dietary ether extract content (EE, %), dietary neutral detergent fiber content (NDF, %) and organic matter digestibility (OMD, %), respectively. Red dotted line (= 110 g/d) represents CH₄ predicted with the reference model and independent variables set to their mean value from the database (i.e. the “true” prediction).

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In case 1 (A), the variability around the “true” prediction, which is the CEDERS database CH₄ mean value at 110 g/day and the value obtained from the reference model when independent variables are set to their mean value from the database (A), was low (CV% = 1.13%). However, in case 2 (B), OMD coefficient was associated with the strongest variability around the “true” prediction with CV% = 10.1%, followed by NDF and EE coefficients with CV% = 3.73 and 2.21%, respectively. The Log DMI coefficient was associated with CV% = 1.41%, highlighting a very low uncertainty. Analysis 2 (Fig. 13) allowed to identify which independent variables explained the most the variation of reference model predictions, represented in case 1 (A).

Fig. 13. Boxplots of CH₄ predicted with the reference model and independent variables randomly drawn in their respective distribution (analysis 2). In case 1 (A), all the independent variables are randomly drawn. In case 2 (B), independent variables are randomly drawn one after the other. Hence, independent variables are set to their mean value from the CEDERS database to do the prediction, except for the considered predictor, log-transformed dry matter intake per day (Log DMI, no unit), dietary ether extract content (EE, %), dietary neutral detergent fiber content (NDF, %) and organic matter digestibility (OMD, %), respectively.

472

473 In case 2 (B), boxplots indicated that Log DMI variability contributed to almost all
 474 prediction variation with a CV% = 81%. Whereas, EE, NDF and OMD were associated
 475 with a very low prediction variation (CV% = 6%, 10% and 7% respectively), highlighting
 476 the low impact of their variability to actual variations of CH₄ production predictions. In
 477 the CEDERS data case, although much larger range of observed values of Log DMI
 478 variable was observed explaining most of CH₄ variations, this was however associated
 479 with a more precise estimation of its regression coefficient.

480

3.3. Issue 3: Omission of a mutation in the data

481

3.3.1. Impact on regression coefficient estimations

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Fig. 14 highlighted biases in coefficient estimates from model 2 (not integrating the
 483 mutation).

484

Fig. 14. Boxplots of estimated regression coefficients for variables log-transformed dry matter intake per day (Log DMI, no unit), dietary ether extract content (EE, %DM), dietary neutral detergent fiber content (NDF, %DM) and organic matter digestibility (OMD, %) of model 1 (integrating the mutation), model 2 (not integrating the mutation) and model 3 (fitted using only mutated individuals of the datasets) developed with datasets from Simulation scenario 2. Red dotted lines represents regression coefficient of the reference model (i.e. the “true” values).

485
 486 The bias is especially strong for Log DMI coefficient, estimated in average at 1.39, for
 487 a “true” value at 0.98. This bias was also observed for other variables but it was much
 488 lower. Model 3 (specific to mutated (small ruminants) part of datasets) and model 1
 489 (five-predictor model explicitly integrating the mutation factor as an additional
 490 independent variable) removed biases over the entire datasets.
 491 Regarding the variability of estimates over the different simulated datasets of
 492 Simulation scenario 2, model 2 showed less variability for Log DMI coefficient (CV% =
 493 0.66% vs 2.34% and 4.14%, for models 1 and 3, respectively), which was associated
 494 with a very strong consistency in the previous analysis. However, this model was
 495 associated with a larger variability than model 1 for the other variables (CV% = 26.8%
 496 vs 17.9% for EE coefficient, CV% = 14.2% vs 10.9% for NDF coefficient and CV% =
 497 20.1% vs 15.1% for OMD coefficient). Although model 3 was developed with less data
 498 than models 1 and 2, variability of these coefficients was similar to model 2, except for
 499 Log DMI (CV% = 27.9% for EE, CV% = 14.0% for NDF and CV% = 19.0% for OMD).
 500 The way the “forgotten” independent variable of model 2 impacted the bias in
 501 coefficient estimates is explored by modifying proportion of mutated or standard
 502 individuals. In Simulation scenario 3, missing data were randomly drawn in the mutated
 503 part of datasets from Simulation scenario 2, using several thresholds. In this way, by
 504 decreasing the presence of the mutation in the data, which initially amounted to 50%
 505 of observations, the mutation is more and more considered as outliers and its weight
 506 on the estimation decreased. Fig. 15 highlighted how increasing the number of mutated
 507 individuals in datasets used to develop model 2 led to a bias increase.
 508

Fig. 15. Bias in log-transformed dry matter intake per day coefficient (Log DMI) (Discrepancy between “true” value from the reference model and mean value of regression coefficients for Log DMI from model 2 fitted on datasets from Simulation scenario 3) according to the number of mutated individuals in datasets.

509
 510 In Simulation scenario 2 (~250 mutated individuals), Log DMI coefficient estimates
 511 corresponded to a weighted average of coefficients specific to each part of the
 512 datasets, mutated or not. However, even when the mutation represented only 10% of
 513 the data (i.e. 25 observations among 275), the bias was still important with an average
 514 estimated regression coefficient at 1.28. This fact highlighted how a few number of
 515 outliers may bias strongly coefficient estimates and led to a wrong interpretation of the
 516 effect of a very important variable. The bias disappeared only when there was no
 517 mutated individuals in the dataset.

518 Ability of models 1, 2 and 3 to predict a test dataset only composed of mutated
 519 individuals (i.e. only of small ruminants) was compared through the RSR values. This
 520 comparison was performed for several proportions of mutated individuals, from 10% to
 521 90%, in datasets used to fit the model. Fig. 16 showed that with mutated individuals
 522 representing 10% of the population (i.e. outliers), difference in performance between
 523 model 2 and models 1 and 3 was important with a difference of RSR of 0.45 and 0.43,
 524 respectively.

525

Fig. 16. Mean value of root mean square prediction error to standard deviation ratio (RSR) of model 1 (integrating the mutation), model 2 (not integrating the mutation) and model 3 (developed using only mutated individuals of the datasets) developed with datasets from Simulation scenario 2 according to the percentage of mutated individuals considered in datasets used for the model adjustment. RSR was computed with a test dataset composed only of mutated individuals.

526

527 This difference decreased when proportion of mutants in the datasets increased. From
 528 a mutation representing 30% of the data, difference of RSR between model 2 and
 529 models 1 and 3 fell to 0.16 and 0.15, respectively, and stabilized around 0.10 when
 530 mutated individuals became majority of the dataset. Model 1 showed a constant RSR
 531 for all the proportions of mutants and was always associated with the lowest RSR.
 532 Even when mutated individuals represented 10% and 20% of the population, model 1
 533 had a lowest prediction error than model 3 with a difference of RSR of 0.02 and 0.01
 534 between both models.

535 *3.3.2. Impact on model predictive performance*

536 Bias highlighted in model 2 had an impact on model predictions (Fig. 17).

Model 1

Model 2

538

Fig. 17. Boxplots of CH₄ (g/day) predicted with model 1 (integrating the mutation) and model 2 (not integrating the mutation) developed with datasets from Simulation scenario 2 (analysis 1). For both models, independent variables are set to their mean value of the database. In case 1 (A), each model gives one prediction, using its own set of estimated coefficients (estimated coefficients vary all together). In case 2 (B), estimated coefficients vary one after the other. Coefficients from the reference model are used to do the prediction, except for the regression coefficient of log-transformed dry matter intake per day (Log DMI, no unit), dietary ether extract content (EE, %DM), dietary neutral detergent fiber content (NDF, %DM) and organic matter digestibility (OMD, %), respectively. Red dotted line represents CH₄ predicted with the reference model and independent variables set to their mean value of the database (i.e. the “true” prediction).

539

540 In case 1 (A), CH₄ predicted with model 2 exhibited an important underestimation of
541 the “true” prediction with a mean value of 74.3 g/day instead of 110 g/day. Predictions
542 from model 1 did not revealed this underestimation (mean value = 109 g/day). In case
543 2 (B), when only Log DMI coefficient moved, an important overestimation was also
544 highlighted for model 2 with a mean value of CH₄ predicted of 223 g/day. Similarly to
545 the study of regression coefficients variability, a bias was also observed for model 2
546 when only coefficients of EE, NDF and OMD moved as mean values of CH₄ predicted
547 stood at 114, 111 and 114 g/d, respectively. Model 1 did not show any bias in case 2.
548 Finally, no difference was observed on prediction variability between both models.
549 Regarding the variability of predictions, similar results to those from the study of
550 regression coefficients variability were obtained. Model 2 was associated with the
551 lowest variability for case 1 (A) and case 2 (B) when only Log DMI coefficient moved
552 with CV% = 1.67 and 1.59 against 2.48 and 3.83 for model 1. Whereas, model 1
553 showed less uncertainty in predictions than model 2 for case 2 when only coefficients
554 of EE (CV% = 2.30 vs 3.06), NDF (CV% = 3.49 vs 4.42) and OMD (CV% = 9.61 vs
555 12.9) moved.

556 **4. Discussion**

557 **4.1. Issue 1: Data transformation**

558 *4.1.1. The log-transformation of CEDERS data allowed to meet assumptions of* 559 *the linear regression*

560 When plotting CH₄ against DMI with the CEDERS data, an heterogeneity of the
561 variability was highlighted between small and large ruminants. This heterogeneity was
562 due to the difference of scale between these two subpopulations, and not to a
563 difference of the underlying biological mechanism (i.e. the rumen fermentation)
564 between small and large ruminants (Malbert et al., 1995). Thus, small ruminants are
565 lighter animals with a smaller rumen. Therefore, they eat lower amounts of feed,
566 meaning a lower amount of matter degraded by the rumen microbiota and less CH₄
567 produced, as compared to larger ruminants. The log-transformation of CH₄ and DMI
568 solved this problem of scale, allowing the homogeneity of variance between small and
569 large ruminants subpopulations, as this transformation scattered low values and
570 grouped dispersed values (Bartlett, 1936; Berry, 1987; Ford, 2018). Several studies
571 (Moder, 2007; Muhamad et al., 2006; Ribeiro-Oliveira et al., 2018) confirmed that data
572 transformation was mandatory when variances are heterogeneous in the data.

573 In addition to the problem of the non-homogeneity of variance between small and large
574 ruminants, the linear regression between CH₄ and DMI using the original data indicated
575 a non-homogeneity of residuals, highlighting that this model did not meet an important
576 assumption of the linear regression. This assumption is essential to avoid an
577 underestimation of the standard error of the slope. When log-transforming CH₄ and
578 DMI, the assumption of residuals homogeneity was met, confirming the importance
579 of the data transformation in our case study. Moreover, a better goodness of fit was
580 highlighted for the regression developed with log-transformed data. However, R² was
581 already very satisfying for the regression developed with the original data. This is
582 explained by the strong known linear relationship between CH₄ and DMI in our case
583 study (Hristov et al., 2013; Niu et al., 2018; Reynolds et al., 2011). However, in the
584 case of such a strong relationship is not present, not applying the data transformation
585 would impact more severely model goodness of fit.

586 From a practical point of view, the main issue with the data transformation is the
587 biological interpretation of transformed regression coefficients (Ahrens et al., 1990;
588 Fernandez, 1992; Ribeiro-Oliveira et al., 2018). This point is crucial and several studies

589 highlighted that data transformation can be inadequate in some situations, affecting
590 the interpretation of results (Fernandez, 1992; O'hara and Kotze, 2010; Valcu and
591 Valcu, 2011). In our case study, the new interpretation of regression coefficients was
592 very relevant to discuss the biological mechanism linking CH₄ production and
593 independent variables. Indeed, the independent variables used in our reference model
594 described the diet composition of the animal and were expressed in percentage,
595 except for Log DMI. Therefore, the interpretation of regression coefficients associates
596 the percentage of increase of components constituting the diet to a percentage of
597 increase or decrease of CH₄ production. In practice, this allows to have a direct
598 interpretation of the effect of diet composition components on CH₄ production, and to
599 compare these effects with each other. Nevertheless, these percentages must be
600 carefully interpreted, by considering the range of variation of the independent
601 variables. For instance, an increase of 1% of OMD and DMI leads to an increase of
602 1% of CH₄ production. However, the range of variation associated with DMI is much
603 larger than the one associated with OMD. Thus, the percentage of increase between
604 the mean and maximum values was of 168% for DMI against 22% for OMD in the
605 CEDERS data. Similarly, in our case study, these percentages should be carefully
606 interpreted when comparing small and large ruminants. An increase of 1% of CH₄ in
607 small and large ruminants does not represent the same amount of CH₄ in g/d. IPCC,
608 2019 proposed to use several CH₄ emissions factors according to the animal category.

609 *4.1.2. The log-transformation of CEDERS data impacted positively model* 610 *predictive performance and prediction uncertainty for the small ruminants*

611 We saw that the data transformation was useful to meet the assumptions to apply the
612 linear regression in our case study. We want now to investigate its impact on model
613 predictions. The evaluation conducted on the overall population of CEDERS data, by
614 implementing a LOO cross-validation and computing the RSR and CCC, highlighted
615 similar performances between both regressions between CH₄ and DMI fitted with the
616 original and log-transformed data. This suggests that the log transformation had no
617 impact on predictive performances. However, when investigating the performances on
618 the two subpopulations composing our data, different results were obtained between
619 both regressions. On small ruminant subpopulation, the regression fitted with log-
620 transformed data showed a better predictive performance than the regression fitted
621 with the original data, highlighting that the log transformation mainly affected small
622 ruminants. While, on large ruminant subpopulation, RSR and CCC were similar
623 between both regressions. This indicates that the data transformation improved the
624 linearity of small ruminant data, while it did not affect large ruminant data. Therefore,
625 the log-transformation was necessary in our case study due to the presence of small
626 ruminants in the CEDERS data. However, the performance on small ruminant data
627 was poor with a RSR above 0.7, even for the regression developed with log-
628 transformed data. This is explained by the poor representation of small ruminants in
629 the overall population (32% of the CEDERS data). Therefore, a lower number of data
630 were available to assess this subpopulation compared to the large ruminants.

631 The positive impact of data transformation on the prediction of small ruminant data was
632 mainly showed when comparing model confidency. Thus, CIs associated with
633 predictions were much narrower for the regression developed with log-transformed
634 data, indicating that these predictions were associated with much less uncertainty than
635 predictions of the regression developed with the original data. When comparing model
636 confidency on large ruminant data, similar CIs were highlighted between both
637 regressions, similarly to what was showed with the evaluation criteria. Moreover, model

638 confidency was slightly higher for the very high values of CH₄. These results
639 highlighted that the impact of the log-tranformation of CEDERS data on model
640 predictions was consistent with the previous analysis, positively affecting the
641 relationship between CH₄ and DMI for the small ruminants.

642 To sum up, our work highlighted that the issue of data transformation is really tricky. In
643 our case study, the two subpopulations associated with two different scales showed
644 an unbalanced representation. This difference of scale mainly impacted CH₄ and DMI,
645 which were associated with a strong positive linear relationship. Large ruminants
646 represented 68% of the data against 32% for the small ruminants. This made difficult
647 to visualize the difference of scale between the two subpopulations when plotting CH₄
648 against DMI. Moreover, when regressing these two variables, this unbalanced
649 representation conducted to a poor impact of the difference of scale on the goodness
650 of fit and evaluation criteria. Therefore, without checking the residuals and model
651 performance and confidency on small and large ruminants, the difference of scale can
652 be missed, leading to a misinterpretation of regression coefficients and of the biological
653 effect of independent variable(s) on the dependent one, and a poor predictive model if
654 small ruminants were more represented. Finally, this pointed out that data
655 transformation can be crucial when applying a parameteric statistical method.
656 However, Ribeiro-Oliveira et al. (2018) also highlighted that transform all the variables
657 studied, even those that do not violate any assumptions, can be a bad decision. In our
658 case study, the heterogeneity of variance between small and large ruminants only
659 affected CH₄ and DMI, justifying their log-transformation in the reference model.
660 Whereas, EE, NDF and OMD were not transformed, as they were associated with the
661 same variability between small and large ruminants.

662 **4.2. Issue 2: Loss of power of the independent variables**

663 *4.2.1. Exploring different data variabilities impacted variable consistency*

664 The impact of data variability on the consistency of variables selected in the reference
665 model was studied by developing models using datasets simulated in Simulation
666 scenario 1 and Simulation scenario 3. The different scenarios of data variability
667 simulated in Simulation scenario 1 were representative of several factors impacting the
668 data used to develop CH₄ emissions models in practice, such as the CH₄ emission
669 measurement method, the region where the study was conducted, and the
670 experimental design and animals used for the experiment. A change of variability from
671 a dataset to another was modeled by considering a perturbation added to the CH₄
672 production. The consistency, which corresponds to the sensitivity of a variable to a
673 perturbation, provides a useful information to study the reliability of a variable.

674 Our results indicated that Log DMI was highly robust to the perturbations simulated in
675 Simulation scenario 1, meaning that its regression coefficient was stable when
676 estimated from a dataset to another. This highlights that Log DMI is a very reliable
677 variable, when interpretating its biological effect on CH₄ production. In animal science,
678 DMI was identified as the key variable to predict CH₄ production in many previous
679 studies (Benaouda et al., 2019b; Hristov et al., 2013; Kriss, 1930; Niu et al., 2018;
680 Reynolds et al., 2011). Therefore, the identification of this variable as highly reliable is
681 a good news, because it means that, when used in a predictive models, its regression
682 coefficient can be interpreted as the direct biological effect of DMI on CH₄ production.
683 Moreover, the inclusion of missing data in Simulation scenario 3 did not affect the
684 significance of Log DMI regression coefficient, highlighting that the effect of Log DMI
685 on CH₄ production was always detected, even when only 50 observations were
686 available for the model development. This reveals that, in addition to its high

687 consistency, Log DMI is not prone to loss of power, confirming its high reliability when
688 interpreting its impact on CH₄ production.

689 The other variables did not highlight the same consistency. Among them, NDF was
690 associated with the second highest consistency, largely lower than Log DMI. NDF was
691 used in many models associated with good predictive performances (Appuhamy et al.,
692 2016; Nielsen et al., 2013; Niu et al., 2018). Moreover, when increasing the number of
693 missing data, its effect on CH₄ production was often detected, even when a small
694 number of observations was available for the model development. Therefore, NDF is
695 also not prone to loss of power and is associated with a good reliability when
696 interpreting its effect on CH₄ production.

697 Whereas, the regression coefficients of EE and OMD were associated with a high
698 variability when estimated with different datasets, indicating a high sensitivity of these
699 variables to the perturbations simulated in Simulation scenario 1. This highlights a low
700 reliability of EE and OMD, when interpreting their biological effects. Therefore, when
701 interpreting their regression coefficients, the impact of EE and OMD on CH₄ production
702 could vary significantly from a sample to another. Moreover, Simulation scenario 3
703 indicated that their effects on CH₄ production could not be detected for small datasets.
704 Indeed, when models were developed with 50 observations, there was a 50% chance
705 that their effects would not be detected from a sample to another. This indicates that
706 EE and OMD were very prone to loss of power and were associated with a low
707 reliability when interpreting their effects on CH₄ production.

708 Furthermore, as expected, Simulation scenario 3 highlighted that increasing the
709 number of missing data was equivalent to decrease the effective sample size and then
710 the precision of estimates for all the variables, which negatively impacted the variable
711 significance.

712 Finally, our work highlighted that some variables identified with a good predictive ability
713 in the literature, such as NDF, could be not significant due to a small perturbation of
714 the data. This perturbation could be representative of the animals used for the
715 experiment, for instance. Therefore, the significance of a variable is not associated
716 with its biological effect. Thus, a variable statistically not significant can have a key role
717 in the biological mechanism under study, although the dataset was not powerful
718 enough to detect its effect. On the other side, a statistical significant variable does not
719 mean a powerful biological effect. Therefore, our recommendation would be to not use
720 the significance as the key criteria for variable selection. A non-significant variable can
721 be retained in a model if the modeler is able to justify its biological effect (literature,
722 assumption in the study...).

723 *4.2.2. Variable consistency impacted model prediction uncertainty*

724 Analysis 2, which assessed the impact of variable variability in the CEDERS data on
725 model prediction variability, indicated that Log DMI explained nearly all the variability
726 of CH₄ predictions. This high contribution was only due to its real variability in the
727 CEDERS data. The other variables were associated with negligible contributions to the
728 variability of model prediction with their own variability.

729 When studying the effect of the variability of regression coefficient estimated with
730 datasets of Simulation scenario 1 on predictions uncertainty, analysis 1 indicated that
731 model predictions associated with Log DMI regression coefficient variation showed the
732 lowest uncertainty. This result was expected, as the previous section highlighted the
733 high consistency of Log DMI. Thus, this variable was largely associated with the
734 highest range of variation but this did not affect prediction uncertainty.

735 When EE regression coefficient varied alone, models' prediction was also associated
736 with a low uncertainty. This was unexpected as EE showed the lowest consistency in
737 the previous analysis but is explained by the low order of magnitude of EE variations
738 compared to other variables. Predictions associated with the variation of NDF
739 regression coefficient alone were associated with the third lowest uncertainty, closed
740 to EE's one. Whereas, predictions associated with OMD regression coefficient
741 variability were associated with the highest uncertainty, although it was not associated
742 with the highest variability of regression coefficients. This difference with the other
743 variables in terms of uncertainty generated on model prediction was due to the
744 combination of the high order of magnitude of OMD and the low consistency of its
745 regression coefficient. This last result highlighted that the uncertainty related to model
746 predictions is the result of the association of several factors, such as the consistency
747 of the variable but also its order of magnitude and range of variation.
748 Finally, in our case study, analyses 1 and 2 revealed that the variable explaining the
749 most the variation of CH₄ predictions was associated with a high consistency. This is
750 a good news in our case study, because the effect of unreliable variables had no impact
751 on model prediction variation. However, this may not be the case in other studies.
752 Therefore, it is important to be cautious about these different aspects.

753 **4.3. Issue 3: Omission of a mutation in the data**

754 *4.3.1. The introduction of a mutation in the data biased regression coefficient* 755 *estimation and impacted negatively model performance*

756 This issue was studied to investigate how a small difference affecting the relationship
757 between dependent and independent variables for some individuals could impact the
758 estimation of regression coefficients, when not considered in the model.

759 When the mutated individuals represented 50% of the data, the results revealed a
760 strong bias for the regression coefficients of model 2, which did not consider the
761 mutation. It was explained by the compromise made by the regression line to fit the
762 two scatter plots associated with mutated and non-mutated subpopulations. The bias
763 was particularly important for Log DMI, while it was low for the other variables. The
764 results of Issue 2 highlighted that the effect of Log DMI was strongly detected, despite
765 the disturbances, which was not the case for the other variables. This suggests that
766 high consistency variables are very sensitive to any modifications affecting the data,
767 while other variables, which were highly prone to loss of power, are not able to detect
768 these changes.

769 Regarding the variability of estimated regression coefficients, model 2 indicated that
770 the non consideration of the mutation did not affect the precision of estimates.
771 Consequently, for model 2, Log DMI regression coefficient was associated with the
772 same precision that model 1, but it did not target the right value (i.e. low accuracy). For
773 the other variables, the results were similar to 4.2.1 for models 1 and 2. Model 3, which
774 was only developed with mutated subpopulation data, showed a lower precision than
775 models 1 and 2. This was expected as a lower number of data was used for the model
776 development.

777 When decreasing the number of mutated individuals in Simulation scenario 3, the bias
778 associated with Log DMI in model 2 also decreased. However, even when the mutation
779 affected only 10% of individuals, which can be considered outliers, the bias of Log DMI
780 was still important with a difference between the estimated regression coefficient and
781 the true value of 0.30. This highlights that the omission of a factor, only modifying the
782 intercept but not the relationship between dependent and other independent variables,
783 in the model development (model 2) strongly negatively impacted regression

784 coefficient estimates, even when this factor affected very few data, similarly to outliers.
785 Moreover, our work revealed that this negative impact was more important for highly
786 robust and reliable variables, such as Log DMI. This suggests that this issue must be
787 considered with a high importance, as robust variables can be considered as important
788 explanatory factors of the biological mechanisms under study, and associating them
789 with biased regression coefficients can lead to misinterpretations of their effect on the
790 dependent variable.

791 The simulation of a mutation affecting part of the data in Simulation scenario 2 also
792 allowed us to investigate the interest of developing a model specific to a subpopulation
793 (model 3) instead of a general model (models 1 and 2). The results revealed that, when
794 compared models 3 and 2 with a mutation affecting 50% of the data, the ability of model
795 3 to predict mutated individuals was much higher than model 2 (RSR = 0.67 vs 0.56).
796 By moving the proportion of mutated individuals in datasets used for model
797 development, we highlighted that increasing the part of mutated individuals
798 significantly improved the predictive performance of model 2. A threshold of 30% of
799 mutated individuals in the data was identified, above which the difference of RSR
800 between models 3 and 2 was less important (< 0.15). However, when 90% of mutated
801 individuals were present in the data (i.e. the non-mutated individuals are then outliers),
802 the difference of RSR between models 3 and 2 was still rather high (= 0.08). This
803 indicates that, as expected, the development of a model specific to a mutated
804 subpopulation, instead of a general model not considering the mutated subpopulation,
805 allowed to improve the prediction of this specific subpopulation. Nevertheless,
806 developing a specific model is a biological question, depending on the interest of the
807 subpopulation in the biological mechanism under study, and only the biologist can
808 answer this question.

809 Finally, when the factor influencing the mutation is clearly identified, which was the
810 case in our case study (the ruminant category), model 1 highlighted that the best option
811 was to include the mutation as a qualitative variable. Even when mutated individuals
812 were outliers, model 1 was associated with a slightly better performance than model 3
813 (RSR = 0.56 vs 0.58, when mutated individuals represented 10% of the data). This is
814 explained by the higher number of data available for developing model 1 compared to
815 model 3. Thus, the main limitation of developing a specific model is the reduction of
816 the number of data available for the development, which means lower model precision
817 and performance.

818 *4.3.2. The bias revealed in regression coefficient estimation impacted* 819 *negatively prediction accuracy*

820 When comparing predictions computed with models 1 and 2, as expected, the bias
821 affecting regression coefficients of model 2 due to the non consideration of the mutation
822 also affected its prediction. Thus, the case 1 indicated that the CH₄ predicted by model
823 2 largely underestimated the true CH₄ value (mean of CH₄ predictions of model 2 =
824 70.4 g/d vs true value = 110 g/d).

825 Moreover, the case 2 revealed that Log DMI regression coefficient variation of model
826 2 led to a large overestimation of the true value (mean of CH₄ predictions of model 2 =
827 211 g/d vs true value = 110 g/d). This is explained by the strong bias highlighted in
828 4.3.1 for the estimated regression coefficients of Log DMI. The predictions of other
829 variables, which were not robust enough to highlight a bias in their regression
830 coefficients, did not reveal any under or overestimation of the true value. Similarly to
831 the section 4.3.1, this was due to the poor ability of these variables to detect any
832 modification in the data.

833 Regarding the variability of predictions, models 1 and 2 were associated with a similar
834 variability, indicating that the consideration or not of the mutation did not affect this
835 aspect, similarly to 4.3.1, as the overall sample size remains the same.
836 Finally, our results revealed that the omission of a structuring factor affecting some
837 individuals, such as a disease, different management practices or a genetic
838 modification, in the model development strongly negatively impacted model
839 predictions. Therefore, the study of this last issue highlighted that including the
840 structuring factor as a qualitative variable in the model development is crucial for both
841 regression coefficient interpretation and model predictive ability.

842 **Conclusion**

843 The impact of three modeling issues (data transformation, loss of power for variable
844 effects detection and omission of a factor in model development) on regression
845 coefficients and predictions of models predicting CH₄ emissions from ruminants was
846 investigated. Our work provided three warnings to modelers: first, not transforming
847 data when required can have negative effects on assumptions of statistical methods
848 and prediction confidence. The interpretation of transformed variables' regression
849 coefficients is then a concern but was relevant in our case of log-transformation.
850 Second, the interpretation of regression coefficients, which may be more or less
851 impacted according to the source of data variability, can be tricky for non consistent
852 variables (i.e. variables prone to lead to loss of power). Our recommendation is to not
853 use variable significance as a key criterion for variable selection. Third, atypical
854 observations can strongly biased regression coefficients and model predictions, even
855 when they concern very few data.

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860 Paul Blondiaux: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal Analysis, Investigation,
861 Methodology, Software, Writing – original draft
862 Maguy Eugène: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Supervision,
863 Writing – review & editing
864 Andre Bannink: Funding acquisition, Project administration, Writing – review & editing
865 Frank Sauvage: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Project
866 administration, Software, Supervision, Writing – review & editing

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870 **Data and model availability statement**

871 The script of the implementation of analyses conducted in this work is available at
872 (Blondiaux, 2024).

873 **Ethics approval**

874 Not applicable.

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880 **Declaration of interest**

881 The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest in relation to the content of
882 the article.

883 **Declaration of generative AI in scientific writing**

884 During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT in order to improve
885 the readability and language of the manuscript. After using this tool/service, the
886 author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for
887 the content of the published article.

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